

RS-III on methylation gave amentoflavone hexamethyl ether⁹ (m.p., R_f , shade in uv light).

RS-IV was crystallised from methanol as yellow needles, m.p. 358–59°, $R_f=0.12$ (BPF, 36 : 9 : 5), brown colour in uv light and green colour with alcoholic FeCl_3 . The uv spectra with diagnostic reagents⁹ showed free hydroxyls at positions 3, 5, 7, 3', 4' and 5', respectively. On acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine it gave the hexaacetate, m.p. 218–19°; δ (CDCl_3) 6.86 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 7.33 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 7.61 (2H, s, H-2', 6'), 2.31 (12H, s, OAc-7, 3', 4', 5') and 2.42 (6H, s, OAc-3, 5). From the spectral data and by direct comparison, it was found to be identical with 3,5,7,3',4',5'-hexahydroxyflavone (myricetin).

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Crystalline Constituents of *Flueggea microcarpa* Blume

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Manuscript received 16 March 1988, accepted 27 July 1988

FLUEGGEA *microcarpa* Blume¹ (Syn. *F. virosa* Roxb., Fam: Euphorbiaceae) is an important medicinal plant found throughout India upto 5000 ft

altitude and in deciduous forests. It has important medicinal property, and the leaves, made into paste with tobacco, is used to kill worms in sores. The roots are used to treat and cure gonorrhea. Earlier workers² reported the presence of alkaloids and the foaming qualities of the plant. Work was done on the pharmacological action of the plant but the extracts were not carefully studied for their crystalline constituents. Hence, a comprehensive and systematic investigation was carried out and the findings are presented herein.

The aerial parts of the plant was powdered and extracted successively with hexane, chloroform and methanol. The hexane extract, after removal of waxes, was chromatographed over silica gel using benzene as the eluent. Three compounds A, B and C were secured. Compound-A was recrystallised from methanol and was identified as β -sitosterol. Compound-B was recrystallised twice from chloroform-methanol as shining needles, m.p. 276°; $[\alpha]_D^{+5}$ (c 1.0 CHCl_3); M^+ 426 (31%); m/e 411 (20%), 302 (100%), 287 (57%), 204 (97%), 189 (23%), 135 (53%), 121 (40%) and 109 (34%). It was identified as taraxerol by a direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p. and co-tl).

Compound-C was recrystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 180–2° (Found (C, 80.50; H, 11.63, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 80.38; H, 11.71%); $[\alpha]_D^{+42}$ (c 1.0 CHCl_3); δ CDCl_3 ; (TMS) 0.85–1.0 (9H), 1.05–1.15 (9H) and 1.5–1.8 (6H); total 24H ($-\text{CH}_2$); δ 3.3–3.1 (br, OH), no peaks in the down-field region; M^+ 444 (9%); with $\text{Py}-\text{Ac}_2\text{O}$, it formed an acetate (crystallised from alcohol), m.p. 169–71° (Found: C, 78.59; H, 11.06, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 79.01; H, 11.11%); $[\alpha]_D^{+54}$ (c 1.0 CHCl_3); δ 0.85–1.0 (9H, $3 \times \text{CH}_3$), 1.05–1.15 (9H, $3 \times$ methyls); 1.5–1.8 (6H, gem-dimethyl adjacent to an oxygen function-supposed to be a bridged oxygen), 2.1 (3H, acetate protons). Compound-C underwent facile oxidation to give a ketone and dehydration with POCl_3 . The above data suggest that it may be a new saturated tetracyclic triterpene with a 3β -OH and an ether bridge in the side chain. The mass spectral data suggest that the ether bridge may be at $\text{C}_{24}-\text{C}_{25}$ position. Further studies to fix the position of the ether bridge, based on chemical and spectral data, confirmed the saturated triterpene structure as 3β -OH, 24–25 ether of lanostane.

The chloroform extract after concentration and crystallisation from CHCl_3 -MeOH failed to give solid, hence it was chromatographed over silica gel using benzene as eluent when two compounds D and E were obtained. From m.p., ir and other spectral data, compound D was identified as lupeol³, m.p. 212°; $[\alpha]_D^{+25}$; the acetate, 221°; $[\alpha]_D^{+41}$ (c 1.0 CHCl_3). Its identity as lupeol was

also confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. In a similar manner, compound-E, m.p. 169–71°; $[\alpha]_D$, was confirmed to be stigmasterol.

The methanolic extract on standing for 48 h furnished a solid (compound-F) which was filtered and crystallised from MeOH as colourless prisms, m.p. 137°; on drying it melted at 237°; $[\alpha]_D$ – 37.7° (c 1.96 EtOH); R_f 0.67 (CHCl₃ – MeOH, 4 : 1); with ferric chloride solution it gave blue colour and it dissolved readily in NaOH solution resulting an yellow coloured solution and could be regenerated on acidification (Found: C, 51.25; H, 4.89. C₁₄H₁₈O₆ requires: C, 51.27; H, 4.88%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 380, 1 701, 1 600, 960 and 850 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} (EtOH) 277 nm (log ϵ 3.98), no shift being observed on the addition of NaOAc or boric acid; δ (CDCl₃/DMSO; 100 MHz, TMS) 3.1–4.1 (6H, m, 11-CH₂, 2,3,4,4a-H), 3.1–4.1 (3H, 3×OH), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.89 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, 10b-H), 5.50 (2H, br, 2×OH) and 7.02 (1H, s, 7-H); M^+ 328 (33%); m/e 208 (100%). Based on the above data, compound-F was identified as bergenin by a direct comparison with an authentic sample⁴⁻⁶. On acetylation, compound-F gave a pentaacetate, m.p. 201°; $[\alpha]_D$ – 42°, and was identified as bergenin 3,4,8,10,11-pentaacetate by direct comparison with an authentic sample. ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃; 90MHz, TMS) of bergenin pentaacetate is in close agreement with that reported; m/e : 496 (60), 454 (88), 418 (39), 405 (31), 376 (54), 376 (60), 334 (40), 321 (50), 293 (21), 292 (95), 279 (65), 274 (100), 261 (50), 259 (47), 250 (45), 237 (37), 236 (18), 224 (52), 221 (30) and 208 (86); R_f 0.59 (C₆H₆ : EtOAc, 3 : 1).

This is the first report of bergenin from this plant. The work on absolute structural elucidation of compound-C, and other new and known triterpene from the methanolic extract is in progress.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor L. R. Row, Andhra University, for his encouragement and valuable suggestions.

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Sterol Composition of *Erigeron karwinskayanus*

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Manuscript received 11 April 1988, revised 8 July 1988, accepted 18 July 1988

ERIGERON karwinskayanus DC (Compositae) is one of the dozen species of genera (*Erigeron*) which grows as perennial herb in hills of Kumaon region especially in Nainital hills. Plants of this genus have been used in indigenous system of medicine¹ and also possess nematicidal properties². Previous investigators have reported the presence of pyrone glycosides³, polyacetylenes and terpenoids⁴ from aerial parts of the plant. However, no work seems to have been reported on sterol composition of the plant. In the course of isolation of nematicidal agents from plant, we isolated the sterol from petroleum ether extract of the plant. The identification and relative concentration of individual sterols are reported here for the first time.

The aerial parts of the plant were collected from the hills of Nainital during July-August, 1987. Dried powdered material (400 g) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a Soxhlet apparatus for 48 h. Evaporations of the extract under reduced pressure afforded a residue (4.5 g), out of which 3.5 g was saponified with 10% methanolic KOH to provide yellow coloured unsaponifiable matter (1.6 g). It was taken up in ether and column chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with hexane followed by increasing amount of ether in hexane (5, 10, 15, 20%) furnished sterols in the last elute. The crude mix. was recrystallised from methanol ether (4 : 1) to provide a crystalline solid, m.p. 130–32°; it gave positive Libermann – Buchard test confirming the steroidal nature of the compound; it was homogeneous on tlc. The sterol was subjected to glc on a Hewlett – Packered 5890 A gas chromatograph fitted with G-Scot glass capillary column (36 m×0.3 mm) coated with DB-17. Temperature of the column, injector and detector were maintained at 255°, 280° respectively. It was found to contain six sterols (Table 1), which were identified by comparison of relative retention time with authentic standard. It was found to contain β -sitosterol as the major component followed by α -spinasterol, stigmasterol dihydro-spinasterol, campesterol and cholesterol. The pre-